

THE ROLE OF PRAGMALINGUISTICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. This article is dedicated to the role and importance of pragmatics and linguopragmatics in linguistics, analyzing issues such as the influence of language on social and cultural situations in society, how it is used in speech activity, and the relationship between language and speech with communicative purposes. The formation of pragmatics in linguistics, its theoretical foundations and practical application, as well as the significance of linguopragmatic research, are discussed.

Keywords: pragmatics, linguopragmatics, speech, communication, social activity, language and culture, phonopragmatics, lexopragmatics, morphopragmatics, syntactopragmatics, speech acts, pragmatic analysis.

Today, the development of philology encompasses not only modern approaches to linguistics and literary studies but also issues such as language and culture, language and society, and linguistic analysis. The advancement of modern linguistics has stimulated the emergence of new scientific fields and methodologies. Among them, new paradigms of linguistics, cultural studies, linguoculturology, psycholinguistics, and computational linguistics deserve special attention.

Language is one of the most important means of expressing human social activity, serving not only as a means of communication but also as a powerful mechanism reflecting the social, cultural, psychological, and spiritual world of an individual. Linguists, in particular, pay great attention to studying the role of language in society and its influence on social activity. One of the important directions in modern linguistics is the analysis of the practical application of language in real life, its consideration as a speech activity, and how it is used in social communication. In these processes, the role of pragmatics in speech and linguistics is of particular importance.

It is known that the practical activity of language manifests itself in speech. However, the speaker must possess a rich reserve of linguistic knowledge and develop the ability to use it appropriately. A person's thinking, national values, culture, customs, and spiritual world are expressed in their thoughts through words. Therefore, in our developing century, it is impossible to approach language directly by "mixing" theories without studying the role and importance of language in the life of society and the individual. The Russian linguist-philosopher G.V. Kolshansky says the following about the subjectivity of language: "Language is a sign of the thinking ability of an individual, a person, all of humanity, and therefore, in its system and structure, it expresses all the features of human mastery of the world, the characteristics of human practical activity, and the conditions of the social and natural environment. Language is both objective and subjective; by its very nature, it is a dual substance, simultaneously addressing being and man."

Initially, studying the language system in isolation from pragmatics does not provide grounds to consider pragmatics as a newly emerged field. This is because there can be no pragmatics detached from language or language detached from pragmatics. While language and human beings are closely intertwined, language serves the speaker's personal desires and needs. A person becomes a participant in communicative situations within the social environment. Therefore, the pragmatic structure is constantly changing and becoming more complex.

Pragmatics is a new theoretical and practical branch of linguistics. It studies the speech process that reflects human social activity, the communicative goals specific to speech participants, issues related to the influence of speech situations, as well as the functional use of linguistic signs in speech. "Pragmatics" (from the Greek "pragmos" - meaning work, action, or performed) is actually a philosophical concept from the 19th-20th centuries. The term "pragmatics" was first introduced by the American scientist Charles Sanders Peirce. Pragmatism began to spread widely, especially in the 1920s and 1930s. The contributions of Charles Peirce, Carnap, Charles Morris, and Wittgenstein to the expansion of American and European pragmatism should be especially noted. The term "pragmatics" was introduced into scientific use by Charles W. Morris in the late 1930s. However, the definition and formation of pragmatics as a field of linguistic research was studied by Z. Vendler in the late 1960s and early 1970s under the influence of logical and philosophical theories of speech acts. In the 1960s and 1970s, with the study of the contextual features of the practical use of linguistic signs in speech, a pragmatic direction began to emerge in linguistics. The formation of linguistic pragmatics is connected with the philosophical views of the eminent scientist L. Wittgenstein, and it is in his works that pragmatics is shown as an independent field of theoretical semiotic research. Linguistic pragmatics began to take shape under the influence of philosophical ideas. Linguistic pragmatics covers the issues of the real expression of the speaker's social activity in speech.

In recent years, numerous studies have been conducted on the subject of linguopragmatics~pragmalinguistics, which is equally relevant to language and speech systems. Among them are works related to the linguopragmatic aspect of sentences. However, the linguopragmatic aspect of most units belonging to all linguistic levels in this field has not yet been fully revealed. Nevertheless, each linguistic unit stored in our memory serves as building material for speech, directly or indirectly participating in the materialization and organization of speech and speech units. In this process, they also acquire semantic functions determined by the speaker, listener, and speech situation, and no linguistic unit is exempt from this. Many issues, such as identifying these meanings and functions, distinguishing them from other meanings and functions, and defining their boundaries, place, and status, are considered problems of the linguopragmatic aspect of a particular speech unit. In short, there is much more to be done in this area, and each aspect, including the linguopragmatic aspect of sentences, requires separate study. At a time when anthropocentric branches of linguistics, such as pragmalinguistics, psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, ethnoinguistics, and cognitive linguistics, are rapidly developing in world linguistics, Uzbek linguists have not remained on the sidelines. On the contrary, they have carried out noteworthy scientific work in almost all of the mentioned areas. The same can be said about the study of language, its activated practical manifestation - speech and the speech units that comprise it, including the problems of the linguopragmatic aspect of sentences. In identifying, defining, and analyzing the

problems of linguopragmatics, renowned linguists N. Mahmudov, A. Nurmonov, Sh. Safarov, M. Hakimov, H. Ne'matov, D. Lutfullayeva, and their students and followers deserve attention and recognition. Their scientific research also contains interesting observations, scientifically based opinions, conclusions, and recommendations on the linguopragmatic features of sentences.

Speech reflects the speaker's social goals, thoughts, and feelings. According to linguists, the study of speech helps to understand the spiritual world of the individual, since language externalizes the information contained in the human mind. Thus, pragmatic analysis carries out a deep analysis of human speech and social activity.

One of the distinctive features of linguopragmatics is its analysis of the interrelationship between language levels. Pragmatics examines the phonetic, lexical, morphological, and syntactic units of language, determining what pragmatic functions each performs and how they achieve the goals of speech. Various approaches, such as phonopragmatics, lexopragmatics, morphopragmatics, and syntactopragmatics, constitute separate branches of pragmatics, each with its own analytical methods. The study of speech act theory, which expresses the essence of linguistic pragmatism, is inextricably linked to revealing the expressive and comprehensible nature of language. All phenomena related to the real world are interconnected; they are synthesized in the mind as tools of cognitive activity through human sensations (sight, hearing, touch) and are re-expressed in language through the act of pronunciation.

Furthermore, pragmatics examines its fundamental concepts, the social and goal-oriented nature of communication, the role of language as an activating tool in communication, and the connection between speech and environment. How speech is used to achieve goals, how explicit and implicit meanings are formed in speech - all these are subjects of pragmatic analysis.

In conclusion, pragmatics is one of the developing scientific directions in modern linguistics, and this field studies issues related to speech processes that reflect the social function of language, communicative goals specific to speech participants, and the influence of the speech situation. Pragmalinguistic analyses are crucial in studying how language influences social and cultural situations in society and the practical application of speech and language.

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